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The conference will be organized in a HYBRID way, which will allow for both physical and online participation of the attendees.

The global economy of the twenty-first century has transformed the economic, social, and political landscape in a profound way. This century has been the scene of revolutions in information and communication technologies, enhanced economic integrations with capital mobility across readers, and a rapidly changing social environment.

In this context, **IRCOBESS 2024**'s main theme is "*New Approaches in Economics and Business: Problems & Opportunities*". In accordance with this, we welcome studies in the fields of economics and business management; also, in branches of social sciences such as public administration, politics, regional studies, and international studies that are related to economics and business management. Studies that are not within the scope of the conference will not be evaluated.

The aim of the conference is to gather leading academicians, policymakers, independent scholars, and researchers to share their knowledge, and new ideas as well as to discuss future development in these fields. It also provides a premier interdisciplinary platform for researchers, practitioners, and educators to present and discuss the most recent innovations, trends, and concerns as well as practical challenges encountered and solutions adopted in the fields of Economics, Business, and Social Sciences.

An additional goal of the **IRCOBESS 2024** is to offer an opportunity for young researchers, academicians, and practitioners with multidisciplinary interests to meet and interact with members inside and outside their own particular disciplines.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE ROLE OF JADIDS IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF TURKESTAN (EXAMPLES OF MONOGRAPHS AND DISSERTATIONS)

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the activities of the Jadids, which are important to study today. In the article, the monographs and dissertations that provide information about the role of the Jadids in the educational system of Turkestan are scientifically analyzed. In the article, the scientific literature on the subject is divided into types and several monographs and dissertations are analyzed. The article describes each literature and provides general information about the literature.

KEY WORDS

Jadids, education, training, local literature, foreign literature, Turkestan, culture, education, muslims, qadims.

The Jadid movement in Turkestan is one of the most controversial and important topics. The contribution of the Jadids to the educational system of the Turkestan region, the state of the educational system before them, the work done by the Jadids in the educational system, new methods of teaching, textbooks and training introduced by the Jadids, the study of literary issues is also relevant. After all, reforms aimed at the development of the educational system and science are being carried out rapidly in Uzbekistan. Therefore, it is important to study in detail the contribution of the Jadids to the educational system, its proper evaluation and research of their scientific-practical heritage related to the educational system, as well as the shortcomings and achievements of the advanced educational system of the Jadids' era.

The scientific researches, which play an important role in elucidating the role of the Jadids in the educational system of Turkestan, can be divided into the following types:

1. Local literature
2. Foreign literature
3. Monographs
4. Dissertations and abstracts
5. Collections
6. Monographs

Monographs are one of the types of scientific works that are considered important for the understanding of the educational system of ancient times. Information on this subject can be obtained from the monographs of such authors as D.Jamolova, U.Dolimov, Z.Abdirashidov, S.Kholboyev, D.Nasretdinova, S.Halimova, T.Qazokov, Y.Yakhshilikhov and N.Ubaidullayeva. Below is a brief analysis of each monograph, highlighting the part related to their research work and its specific aspects: D.Jamolova's monograph "Activities of Jadids and Qadims in the Emirate of Bukhara (late 19th - early 20th century)". On the basis of historical sources, periodical press materials and archival documents, the monograph deals with socio-political processes in the Bukhara Emirate in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, the political activities of Amir Abdulahad Khan and Amir Olim Khan, the emergence of the Jadidism movement and the activities of its opponents. The parts of the monograph about the Yangu method schools are important for the research [6].

U.Dolimov's monograph "Jadid Schools in Turkestan". This book is one of the important primary literature for research.

The book deals with the history of Jadid schools in Turkestan and their development processes. It also deals with the teaching of mother tongue and literature in Jadid schools, charity societies, and issues of struggle between antiquarians and Jadids. The first textbooks and study guides produced by the Jadids at the beginning of the 20th century are also analysed in detail [5].

Z.Abdirashidov's monograph "Jadidism in Turkestan". The work analyses the facts about the Jadidism movement that began to form in Turkestan at the beginning of the 20th century, the obstacles that the Russian government put in the way of the development of this movement, the effects of the policy of denial and Russification on Jadidism and its representatives, and the activities of the mature representatives of Jadidism. The work consists of seven chapters, and the second chapter (*Jadid schools - the foundation of the great future*) and some other parts of the work are important for illuminating the chosen topic [2]. The monograph entitled "Turkistan Jadidism - the history of the period of national renaissance (end of the 19th century - beginning of the 20th century)". In this work, written by a team of authors, the socio-political, cultural-educational, cultural-secular, ideological struggle against Muslim bigotry, which was an obstacle to social and secular progress, science and reformism, and the imperialist and communist colonialism of Russia, is described. - The history of the ideological movement of Jadidism and its representatives and the national awakening renaissance in Turkestan at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th centuries has been researched on the basis of available documents and literature. The work consists of five chapters, the first of which is entitled "Emergence and development of modern national secular public education in Turkestan" and the fourth of which is entitled "Formation of modern national history and geography sciences and education in Turkestan". D.Nasretdinova's monograph "Tatar women in the cultural life of Turkestan". This work is devoted to the changes that took place in the cultural life of Turkestan in the early years of the colonialism

of the Russian Empire and the Soviet power, as well as to the mutual cooperation of Uzbek and Tatar women in the cultural and educational spheres during these processes.

The work is divided into three chapters, the first of which is important in illuminating the educational system of the Jadid era. The first chapter is entitled "The role of Tatar women in the educational system of Turkestan at the end of the 19th century - the first quarter of the 20th century".

S.A.Halimova's monograph "Ubaidulla Asadullakhojaev and Sadoi Turkistan". This work deals with the ideas of the first Uzbek jurist, the editor-in-chief of the newspaper "Sadoi Turkistan" Ubaidulla Asadullakho'jayev, who led the struggle for national liberation in Turkestan in 1914-1915. The work consists of three chapters, and the section of the second chapter (*Interpretation of the socio-political life, educational and spiritual problems of the country in the newspaper "Sadoi Turkistan"*) describes the educational system of that period.

T.Q.Kazakov's monograph "Jadid Movement in the Fergana Valley". In this monograph the origin, formation, stages of development of the Jadid movement in the Fergana Valley, the educational activities of the Jadids and their role in the establishment of the Turkestan Autonomy are discussed in detail. The work consists of two chapters: the first one is called "The emergence and formation of Jadidism in the Fergana Valley", the second one is called "The cultural-educational and socio-political activity of the Jadids of the Fergana Valley at the beginning of the 20th century". Information about the activities of the Jadids in the field of education is given in the second chapter [11].

The monograph "Jadidism and Behbudiy" by J.Yakhshilikov and N.Ubaidullaeva. This work is dedicated to Mahmudhoja Behbudi from Samarkand, a prominent representative of the Jadidist movement and his enlightening activities. The work consists of four chapters and is considered one of the most important research literature [18].

Dissertations and abstracts are the next type of scientific literature that is important in covering the research work. The dissertations of researchers such as D.M.Jamolova, S.E.Normamatov, N.Q.Ahmedov,

N.B.Komilov, N.I.Alimova, N.N.Kadirov, A.M.Mahmudov, F.U.Temirov, M.S.Kadirova, and Kh.S.Ashurova are important in illuminating the education of the Jadidist era in Turkestan.

The dissertations and abstracts of these researchers are analyzed below, and their specific aspects are highlighted: D.M.Jamolova "The Activities of the Jadids and Qadims in the Emirate of Bukhara (Late 19th Century - Early 20th Century)". The dissertation consists of an introduction, three chapters, a conclusion, a list of sources and references, and an appendix. The first chapter of the dissertation, entitled "Historical Roots of the Jadidism Movement in the Emirate of Bukhara", is devoted to the questions of the role of Abu Nasr Kursavi, Shahabuddin Marjani and Ahmed Donish in the emergence of the progressive movement in Bukhara and the reforming activities of Amir Abdulahad Khan. The second chapter of the dissertation is entitled "Different groups of the progressive movement in Bukhara and the relations between them". The third chapter, entitled "Intensification of the conflicts between the Jadids and the old-timers", examines the Emir's decree of 1917 and the reaction of the Jadids and the old-timers to it, the situation of the old-timers and the old-timers in the period after the Kolesov campaign, and the reaction of the old-timers and the old-timers to the events of September 1920 [7]. S.E.Normamatov "The Role of Modern Enlighteners in the Formation and Development of the Uzbek Vocabulary". The thesis consists of an introduction, four chapters, a conclusion and a list of literature used. The first chapter, entitled "Jadid Enlighteners and Contemporary Linguistics", analyses the concepts of "Jadid" and "Jadidism", schools and directions of Jadidism, and the activities of Jadids in language and linguistics. In the second, third and fourth chapters, the issues of lexicology and the activities of Jadids in this field and their importance were considered [14]. N.Q.Ahmedov "Cultural life in Namangan uyezd at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century". The thesis consists of an introduction, two chapters, a conclusion, an appendix and a list of references. The first chapter is entitled "Social and political situation in Namangan district at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century".

This chapter discusses the end of the Ko'kan khanate, the creation of the Namangan district, and the socio-political and cultural situation in the district. The second chapter is called "Specific aspects of cultural life in Namangan uyezd at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century". N.B.Komilov "Life, socio-political, cultural activity of Obidjon Mahmudov from Turkestan Jadids (1871-1936)". The dissertation consists of an introduction, three chapters, a conclusion and a list of sources and references. The first chapter of the dissertation, entitled "The Place and Role of Obidjon Mahmudov in the Jadidist Movement", consists of two paragraphs. This chapter provides information about the historiography of the legacy of the leader of the Kokhan Jadids, Abidjon Mahmudov, some aspects of his life and activities, his activities in Moscow (1918-1921) and his descendants. The second chapter of the dissertation is called "The place and role of Abidjon Mahmudov in the national press and publishing house", it reflects the importance of the newspaper "Sadoi Fergana" in the socio-political, economic and cultural life of the society, as well as the role of Abidjon Mahmudov in the press as a publisher and journalist. The third chapter of the dissertation is called "Obidjon Mahmudov's statecraft". It describes Obidjon Mahmudov's activities as a deputy of the Kokand City Duma, deputy chairman, and the establishment of the Turkestan Autonomy, as well as Minister of Food. The chapter justifies Abidjon Mahmudov's enthusiasm for the organization of the Kokand Stock Exchange, his socio-economic views, and his unjust accusation and repression by the Soviets, as well as the confiscation of his property [8]. N.I.Alimova "The policy of tsarist Russia in the field of national culture in Turkestan (1867-1917)". The dissertation consists of an introduction, three chapters, a conclusion and a list of sources and references. The first chapter, entitled "The Tsarist Government's Policy of Restricting National Education in Turkestan", deals with the Tsarist attitude towards the activities of madrasahs and schools, the weakening of the material base of madrasahs and the control over educational activities. The second chapter is entitled "The emergence, development and struggle of tsarism against the Jadid schools".

This chapter discusses the establishment of Jadid schools and the problems of their operation.

The third chapter is called "The appropriation of the cultural heritage of the people of Turkestan by the tsarist government" and deals with the plundering of valuable works, archival documents and monuments of material culture that were taken from the country [3]. N.N.Kadyrov "History of Russian educational institutions in the Turkestan region (1867-1917)". The thesis consists of an introduction, three chapters, a conclusion, a list of sources and literature used, and an appendix. The first chapter is entitled "The state of the traditional education system in Turkestan and the attitude of the colonial authorities to it".

In this chapter, the state and characteristics of the traditional educational system of the country at that time are explained, as well as the attitude and policy of the Russian Empire towards the educational system, its content and nature. The second chapter, entitled "The system of education management in the Turkestan region and the formation and operation of Russian educational institutions", analyses materials on the opening and operation of new types of central and local schools, and then on the opening and operation of Russian and Russian-system schools. The third chapter is entitled "Introduction and activity of the secondary and vocational education system in Turkestan".

This chapter contains information on grammar schools and vocational secondary schools that served to promote the Russian education system. The dissertation is important because it provides valuable information about the state of the educational system before the new school in the country and the Russian system schools, which were competitors of the Jadid schools [9].

A.M.Mahmudov "Social and political activity of Usman Khoja Polathojaev". The dissertation consists of an introduction, three chapters, a conclusion, a list of used sources and literature and an appendix. The first chapter of the dissertation entitled "Factors influencing the formation of socio-political views of Usman Khoja Polathojaev and his participation in the revolutionary movement" is important for the research work.

It examines the situation in Rif, the factors that influenced Usman Khoja's worldview and its theoretical foundations, the educational activities of the progressives, and the participation of the Bukhara Emirate and Turkestan in the Jadidist movement.

The second chapter of the dissertation, entitled "Research of the activities of Usman Khoja Polathojaev in the government of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic (BSSR)", deals with the responsible tasks performed by Usman Khoja in the government of the BSSR, his participation in solving economic, social and cultural problems of the new government's domestic and foreign policy, and analyses the historical processes. The third chapter of the dissertation is called "Usman Khoja's life and work in emigration" and discusses the reasons for his emigration abroad, his struggle for national unity and independence of Turkestan abroad, his organizational and journalistic activities as one of the leaders of Turkestan people, and the spiritual legacy he left to the present generation. 12]. F.U.Temirov "The Role and Social Activity of Sadriddin Aini in the Jadidism Movement in Bukhara". The study consists of an introduction, three chapters, a conclusion, a list of sources and references, and an appendix. The first chapter of the dissertation, entitled "Sadriddin Ainiy - an important representative of the Jadidism movement in Bukhara", is devoted to the analysis of issues such as Sadriddin Ainiy's participation in the Jadidism movement in Bukhara, his role, social activities, reformist and enlightened views. The second chapter of the dissertation, entitled "Social Activities of Sadriddin Aini in Uzbekistan and Tajikistan", contains information about the press and training activities of Sadriddin Aini, a brilliant scientist and writer who made a great contribution to the development of the literature and history of the Uzbek and Tajik peoples, as well as a scientific and public figure. The third chapter of the dissertation, entitled "Interpretation of the Jadidist Movement and Social Issues in the Works of Sadriddin Ainiy in the Bukhara Emirate", shows the achievements of Sadriddin Ainiy in historical and political events, such as the spread of progressive, enlightened and reformist ideas in the Bukhara Emirate, the opening of new method (Jadid) schools, through the analysis of sources.

The issues of the history of Turkestan and Bukhara were also studied through the scientific analysis of his work "History of the Mangit Amirs of Bukhara" and a number of journalistic articles [15].

M.S.Kadirova "Ibrahim Davron and his literary legacy". The dissertation consists of an introduction, three chapters, a conclusion and a list of literature used. The first chapter is called "Jadidchilik and Ko'kan literary environment" and it describes the Jadidlik movement and its socio-educational nature and the role of the Kokan Jadidlik school in the life of the society. The second chapter of the dissertation is entitled "Ibrahim Davron's literary legacy" and it examines the issues of Ibrahim Davron's life and work, journalism, translations and graphic paintings. In the third chapter, the place of "Ash'ori Nisvan" in the literary heritage of Ibrahim Davron, the "Ash'ori Nisvan" complex and its specific features are analyzed from a literary point of view[10].

H.S.Ashurova "Social and political views of Samarkand Jadids (first quarter of XX century)". The dissertation consists of an introduction, three chapters, a conclusion and a bibliography. In the first chapter, entitled "Specifics of socio-political views in the doctrine of Jadidism in Samarkand", such issues as the social reasons for the emergence of Jadidism, the conditions of the end of the XIX and the beginning of the XX century, and the beginning of the activities of Jadidism in Samarkand were considered. The second chapter of the thesis is called "The harmony of ideas of modernization and innovation in the doctrine of the Jadids".

In this chapter, such issues as the modernization of society on the principle of modernizing the social life and way of life of the ancients, raising all spheres to a new level, i.e. the stage of modernization on the basis of the changes that have taken place in Europe, are analyzed. The third chapter of the dissertation is called "The Role of the Teachings of the Samarkand Jadids in the Development of the Social Position and Political Consciousness of Young People". The Jadids of Samarkand were deeply aware of the need to fundamentally reform the educational system for the sake of the country's freedom and liberty.

Mahmudhoja Behbudi, who was the leader not only of the Samarkand Jadids but also of the Turkestan Jadids, emphasized that the role of education in the development of society was extremely important and wrote: "A nation without the benefit of science and knowledge of the time will be a burden to other nations.

As science and technology developed in the West, the modern Enlightenment paid great attention to sending young people abroad for education.

According to them, it is not enough to study only in national schools, but it is advisable to study in higher educational institutions of the developed countries of the West and the East in order to acquire science and technology as well as social and humanitarian sciences. These issues are considered in this chapter [4].

In conclusion, it can be said that the analysis of the literature divided into the above-mentioned types and its application in scientific work increases the thoroughness and perfection of the research work. In addition, it ensures the consistency and reliability of the work, as well as its speed and simplicity. In the process of analyzing the literature on the topic, the information in the literature was compared and determined. In this case, studying the information in the literature on the basis of a comparative analysis helps to logically avoid errors and repetition of research. In short, the literature analyzed above is important in explaining the role of jadids in the educational system of Turkestan.

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